

Fertilizer management—organic sources

Influence of green manure (GM) *Sesbania aculeata* on Zn and S translocation in rice

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We evaluated the effect of GM *S. aculeata* on translocation of Zn and S to the grain, straw, and roots of short-duration rice variety ADT36 using ^{65}Zn and ^{35}S radioisotopes in a greenhouse experiment. Zn was applied to soils as ZnSO_4 or EDTA-Zn at 1.0 m Ci/g Zn and S as gypsum at 0.2 m Ci/g S. A black, calcareous clay loam (Vertic Ustropepts) with pH 8.0, EC 0.51 dS/m, 0.56% organic C, 58 ppm total Zn, and 200 ppm total S and a red, noncalcareous sandy loam (Typic Haplustalf) with pH 7.1, EC 0.13 dS/m, 0.45% organic C, 47 ppm total Zn, and 180 ppm total S were used. Recommended levels of NPK were applied.

ZnSO_4 + gypsum + GM recorded the highest percent translocation to the grain of total Zn absorbed in both the clay loam (56.5%) and sandy loam (53.2%) (Table 1). More Zn accumulated in straw with EDTA-Zn than with ZnSO_4 . Zn retention in roots was highest with ZnSO_4 + GM (37.3%) in the clay loam and with EDTA-Zn + GM (49.4%) in the sandy loam. This high retention of Zn in roots without translocation evenly to grain and straw, especially with GM, reflects excessive Zn consumption.

Similarly, an increased translocation to grain of absorbed S occurred with gypsum + GM in both soils, with 42.3% in clay loam and 45.0% in sandy loam (Table 2). Sulfur supplied from the GM might have helped in the higher absorption and translocation of S to grain as compared with its translocation to straw and roots. Information reported is from a tracer study; sufficient replications could not be included to establish facts by statistical significance. ■

Table 1. Percent translocation of ^{65}Zn from applied fertilizer measured at harvest stage.*

Treatment	Clay loam			Sandy loam		
	Grain	Straw	Root	Grain	Straw	Root
ZnSO_4	51.5	22.3	26.3	40.4	32.7	26.9
EDTA-Zn	53.3	27.2	19.6	29.3	41.1	29.5
ZnSO_4 + GM	33.8	29.0	37.3	33.9	27.1	39.0
EDTA-Zn + GM	42.1	31.0	26.8	32.6	18.0	49.4
ZnSO_4 + gypsum + GM	56.5	16.4	27.1	53.2	15.0	28.6

*Mean of two replications. Data not statistically analyzed.

Table 2. Percent translocation of ^{35}S from applied fertilizer measured at harvest stage.*

Treatment	Clay loam			Sandy loam		
	Grain	Straw	Root	Grain	Straw	Root
Gypsum	36.4	40.7	23.0	39.0	49.1	11.9
Gypsum + GM	42.3	39.6	18.2	45.0	41.0	14.1
Gypsum + ZnSO_4 + GM	38.6	42.6	18.9	45.9	40.8	13.2

*Mean of two replications. Data not statistically analyzed.

Biofertilizers enhance dissolved oxygen content (DOC) in water

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Continuous cultivation of blue-green algae (BGA) and azolla is suspected to cause pollution. A study of BGA and azolla nurseries under continuous submergence for more than a year, however, revealed an enhanced DOC in the water. DOC increased between 0600 and 1600 h but declined thereafter.

Between 0600 and 1600 h, DOC ranged from 3.7 to 7.1 ppm in the BGA nursery, from 1.3 to 5.5 ppm in the azolla nursery, and from 3.1 to 5.4 ppm in the control where water was impounded without BGA or azolla. Most samples from the BGA nursery had higher DOC than did those from the control. DOC in the control was higher than that in the azolla nursery, except at 1600 h (Table 1).

CO_2 evolution was 61 mg/h per m^2 in the azolla nursery, which was more than in the BGA nursery (46 mg/h per m^2) and control (10 mg/h per m^2) (Table 2). Although CO_2 emissions may contribute

Table 1. DOC and temperature in BGA and azolla nurseries at TNRRI, Aduthurai, India, Jun-Sep 1992.

Parameter	Sampling time (h)						
	0600	0800	1000	1200	1400	1600	1800
	<i>Dissolved oxygen^a (ppm)</i>						
Control	3.1	5.4	5.3	5.0	5.0	4.7	4.2
BGA nursery	3.7	4.5	6.0	6.8	6.9	7.1	4.2
Azolla nursery	1.3	2.2	3.9	4.2	4.5	5.5	3.3
	<i>Temperature^a (°C)</i>						
Control	25	29	33	38	42	37	32
BGA nursery	25	29	34	38	41	36	32
Azolla nursery	23	28	30	34	39	34	31

*Mean analysis of 2 d.